

CONTENT ANALYSIS OF “LOVE LEADS TO PAIN” AS ONE OF THE MAJOR THEME OF HEMINGWAY’S NOVEL, A FAREWELL TO ARM

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ABSTRACT

This study analyses Hemingway’s novel a farewell to arm with a purpose to make it easy for the readers, and to understand one of the major themes of the novel ‘love leads to pain’. The method being used for this study is textual analysis under the umbrella of qualitative research paradigm. Moreover, in this novel the protagonist Henry’s physical love transforms into spiritual love and in the end, he suffers psychologically because of the death of his beloved Catherine.

Love is a cognitive emotion and most of the time it faces failure or loss of the beloved and further it leads to psychological pains that are overwhelming for humans. This study leaves a gap for the other researchers to get through the novel and find out that merely pain is not the outcome of love, there are some other unfavourable that factors can be the causes of it.

Keywords: Love, pain, analysis, farewell, arms, leads

INTRODUCTION

The novel “A fairwell to arms written by Hemisngway, published in1977. It contains 41 chapters,that revolves around the story of an American nurse Catherine and the protagonist an Army ambulance driver Henry. The story starts with the feelings of lust but afterwards the lust transforms into pure love. They both enjoy love with the great excitement even during war. Sometimes, they have to part from each other, due to their professional obligations. But they have a longing for each other. As the time passes, sometimes destiny would not be in the favour of human expectations. So they part in the end due to the illness as she died of brain hamerriage. The story ends with the separation of the lovers.

Human beings are blessed with feelings like love, hate, happiness, sadness, anger and so on. These feelings are thought to be having psychological appeal to human emotions. As we know that emotions don’t need reasons, yet they are resulted from timely actions. These conditions

can be attachment, profit, loss or professional jealousy and so on. These conditions bring about results in the shape of feelings. One of these conditions is the attachment between opposite sexes which can rightly be called as love.

According to Sternberg(1986) Love is itself a triangle of three elements such as intimacy, passion and commitment. Intimacy is an element of closeness of two souls. It can be in close friendship that comes in the closeness of two people. The element of passion is that it happens due to charming and attractive feelings between two people when both have the desires for living together. The element of commitment is that when two people want to live together not for the time being but forever’ to lead a life with each other (Robert Stemberg).

Humans have a loving nature that changes into attraction between two people, when a couple spends beautiful time together. Their feelings are elated which brings about attractions which has

durable physiological reflection in the shape of love (Kane).

Love is actually a want of someone to have someone for a long time or even for life time. It becomes severe as the relation becomes stronger. With the passage of time it is increasing, so it needs to have a union in shape of marriage. If marriage happens between the two, then it is almost fulfilled and changes into another form, and in case, it fails to bring the two souls together, then it leads to psychological pain which afterwards becomes physical as well. Even love still needs explanations because it is sometimes called as a divine spirits and sometimes the relation of souls. Yet I would prefer to the words of Elizabeth Kane, who says that falling in love is the first step when we meet a person of our choice then occurs various changes in our mood, that would be the feeling of pleasure. At the same time our heart starts giving positive and charming signals while meeting or talking that person (Elizabeth Kane).

This study analyzes “Love leads to Pain” as one the leading themes in Heming way’s novel, “A Farewell to Arms” .a brief analysis of the opinions of some experts is as under.

Research objectives

To find out the effects of love on human mind, when it faces failure or loss of the beloved.

- To highlight impact of love which turns into pain.
- Aftermath of loss of love.
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Research questions

- How would love be define?
- Describe psychological pain as a result of love?
- State whether love always results in pain?
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Literature Review

Earnest Miller Hemingways was born on July 21, 1899. He is one of the top of American novelists, short story writer and also Journalists. He had a great impact on 20th century fiction. He got praises from late generation through his way of living as a courageous soul. Hegot most of his work published between the 1920’s and 1950’s. He received the noble prize in literature in 1954. He produced seven novels, six short story collections, four short story collections and three

non-fiction works. Mostly he worked on American Literature. It was in his mastery of the narrative that was found in ‘The old man and the sea’. His other novel ‘A farewell to Arms’, which was writtenduring the Italian campaign of World War-I. This novel was published in 1929. The novel depicts a love affair between Henry; an emigrant from America and an English nurse Catherine Barkley. The story starts between two love birds Catherine and Henry, depicts spiritual and pure love. Their love goes smoothly, both of them spend their days together without chaos. The protagonist Henry remains YESMAN, in the entire novel, whereas Catherine, shows pure love, care and supportive behavior towards him. But in the last as this world is mortal and everyone has to leave this world once for all. So, the dramatic and painful situation happens after a long lovable journey of life spent by both of them together. So they are defeated by their fate and Catherine has to leave the world as she was suffering from hamerrage, which happened continuously and as a result she passed away. Henry had to live without her. Perhaps, it was doom to their destiny. Such pure and lovely love turns into pain. As Henry has to live under umbrella of pain in the absence of Catherine forever. Therefore, Henry is affected psychologically in the end of the novel. In this novel, “ a farewell to arms” Hemingways presents the definition of love through the character priest. His definition of love is quite different from that of general point of view of love; he explains love in a religious perspective by declining the lust as love but he presents love as divine spirit between two souls. (Yari, 2019).

There is no relationship between love and war; war is inhumane, whereas love appeals to emotions. In ‘a farewell to arms’ The writer depicts the scenario love under the shade of ammunition. When war is dominant everywhere, the true lover (Henry) leaves the war and goes for love. In this article the writer shows the two situations simultaneously, that of war and that of love. The protagonist (Henry), who gives preference to love than war. He considers war as a toxic and the signal of danger for the humanity, while love as a paradise for the mankind as Plato quotes that love is the straight, smooth and beautiful path for the solution of all the hurdles and difficulties. Hemingway’s novel, “A Farewell to Arms” is in autobiographic novel in which he

tells us his real story when he was in love with an American nurse Agnes; who rejected his love which caused him both physical and psychological pain' through the characters of Catherine and Henry which ends at the death of Catherine, which leaves Henry in a plight of psychological pain.(karmakar, 2020)

Psychoanalytical Framework

The present study titled love leads to pain is a prominent theme in earnest Hemingway novel a farewell to arms can be related to psychoanalytical theory because this study presents the psychological pain being faced by Henry. Psychological theory is a theory given by Sigmund Freud in which he says: the conscious deals with cognitive matters which takes place in the present situation it is present in the iceberg under this part of the mind. As the available memories are present in the pre-conscious mind while preconscious mind is in the conscious mind. A person takes out memories into the conscious mind from his preconscious mind. Both conscious and preconscious mind are parallel to each other. According to him these two layers are connected to the tiny part of the mind. Whereas, all the past events that are not easily found in the conscious mind, they can easily be drawn out from the unconscious mind. The conscious mind is the vital part of the human brain which plays an important role in personality of a person. It is the place where wishes, desires, feelings and impulses are being stored. The unconscious mind plays the role of a referee in determining the behavior of the human. (Sigmund Freud) It is astonishing about psychoanalytical theory, that it gives more importance to the unconscious imagination of man and his cognitive struggle to combat with himself and society while on the other hand it gives less importance to his desires and lust. (Laplanche and Contelis 1973) In this study, it is found that love leaves long lasting marks on human brain which are painful for a long time. It happened to Henry after losing his love Catherine as narrated in the story of the novel. At the end he is left in isolation with the burden of psychological pain for the rest of his life. Sometimes, we have to suppress our cognitive thoughts, in order to live in the society peacefully. Whenever, we don't meet the satisfactory level of our mind, we have to work upon regulations of

our emotions, to bring under them control, so as to achieve goal (leCroy 2000). According to Weston, Cognitive emotions play a vital role in the personality development of an individual. Moreover, self-progress deals with the ability which helps to bring control over internal emotions consciously (Westen 1998).

CONTENT ANALYSIS

(A Farewell to Arms Page, 16, 17, 18)

Catherine has fear of wars as she has lost her fiancé in the war: as she is (has been) 08 year engaged with him. Therefore, she has pain of being parted from him. Therefore she feels fear again in love because, she has lost her previous fiancé already. Therefore the absence/missing of her fiancé makes her love turned into pain.

I sat in the reception hall of the villa, waiting for Catherine I was feeling lonely and hollow.

(A Farewell to Arms Page, 34)

When Henry wants to meet Catherine then, he goes to hospital. He waits for her but he could not meet her due to some certain reasons as she did not come to the hospital. The absence of Catherine makes him upset as he is longing for her. He remains silent and gets back to his place. He starts something in his heart and begins to miss her. He feels something vacant and feels isolated.

It proves that distance between true lovers increases the intensity of love and if one of them is missing, from the place where they were supposed to meet, the other suffers which is the result of love and as is said, "love turns into pain". So Henry while missing her, suffers mentally which is the possible result of love.

No I don't want to hear about it.....i will be so faithful.

(A Farewell to Arms Page 85-86)

When Catherine talks about her late fiancé that she was loved by him and waited for eight long years. Henry does not like talk of third person between them, even he doesn't like to listen the connection of Catherine with someone else: it clearly shows that he is in deep love with her, whenever he listens about her, he gets hurt and demands Catherine to be loyal with him and definitely, he will marry her whenever, she wants,

because, he does not want to be betrayed by her. Therefore, his true love turns into pain. Whenever, he thinks about the other person, he says, "don't leave me for someone else: Similarly, Catherine asks her don't leave her too for someone else.(A Farewell to Arms Page, 231-236) When Catherine is taken to the hospital during her labour pain was going on, she doesnot bear the labour pain continuously, and haemorrhage took place. After watching Henry remains upset and begins to pray for her health. Even he is that much unconscious that he doesn't care about his son that either he is alive or not. He is only worried for Catherine.He wants her to be fine and get back to him as soon as possible but it does not happen the condition of Catherine getting worst.In this condition, when someone losses her beloved and watch her on death bed and thinking make crazy that she would be no more with him, then how much painful situation it would be. Similarly Henry feels the situation of being restlessness and helplessness, as he would not be able to live without her. He weeps and mourns a lot and her absence made him empty and hollow.In the last scene of the novel, that is painful for the reader also two love birds are getting parted and never meet again as one is passed away and the other has to live alone. That is traumatic situation for the reader which hurts the cognitive feelings of the person as is faced by Henry. He always remain YESMAN in the entire novel and prefers to love than war. He leaves everything for Catherine but in last he loses Catherine that shakes his life which proves that love turns into pain.

You are not really afraid of the rain are you?.....on raining.

(A Farewell to Arms Page, 93).

She always remain fearful; when the rain starts showering, she has the fear of parting. Once she says that rain will part them.Rain makes her terrifiedfor being parted from Henry. Fear and disparity also cause suffering of love. She does not want to get separated from him, whenever, it rains, she feels that it will cause separation from Henry. She doesnot want to live a single minute without him. She wants to see kids together with him as she loves him heart and soul. Therefore, she wants to live happily with him for good.

Discussion

In this novel the writer present love in a smooth manner which goes on whatever the situation may have been. The Characters have nothing to do with the surroundings. Firstly, they begin with conversation then meetings on daily basis and later on their frequent physical approaches and the intimacy goes on. Sometimes they get parted. Such temporary partitions don't make any problem for them because they have the opportunity to meet again and again. They have no fear of losing each other for ever. Catherine looks perfectly satisfied with her love Henry. She has many qualities that make her character a positive a good and positive character.She deals to Henry in an optimistic manner, by being loyal, caring, and supportive to him. She is confident of Henry and has no fear of betrayal from his side that Henry would go for someone else at the same time. She cannot even think of being deceived by him. She loves and cares Henry so much that she manages her pregnancy without marriage to him, yet she does notdisturb him emphasize him for marriage, so that he may not stuck in social bounds which as a result will make his life a hell. So she remains positive and loyal everywhere and does not show scornfulness or detest and never use bad language for him in the period of her pregnancy for almost nine months.Whereas, Henry; the protagonist of the novel, is also positive, sensible, obedient and honourable person, who is restless person for his love all the times. He remains obedient and kind to Catherine. He has spares his life for Catherine and his all actions are for the betterment of Catherine. Even, firstly, he is not interested in love, his interest is only physical but as far as he has quality time with Catherine, his lust turns into deep love. A time comes when he feels himself in love with her which is increasing day by day.Further, he sighs for her and misses her wherever he goes anywhere or does anything or meets or talks with other women. Simultaneously, he feels missing Catherine, imagines to talk to her. He expresses his feelings for her while eating, drinking and even sleeping. His loyalty can be felt in his imagination. Moreover, when she asks him to marry her, he does not refuse. Almost of his responses are in positive always. In other words he has become a "Yesman" for his love while caring nothing else in his surroundings. In short, when he becomes

a true lover, he remains obedient lover all the time in the novel. When there is true love it results there is pain. The writer presents the true and beautiful love story of loyal, positive and supportive characters like Henry and Catherine that are smoothly living a life full of happiness and joy. There is a turning point in the last chapter of the novel, where fate defeats love. It dooms the love into pain. Catherine is having a continuous hamerdge and is on her death bed which is unbearable for Henry because he is helpless and can do nothing. So it becomes a hard dilemma for him. He prays to god not to take away his love. By nature, this is painful moment for the true lover, when his/ her beloved is in the death bed and a lot of thoughts are hurling in his mind that he is going to lose his love or would never meet, talk, sit, sleep and never share beautiful moments with the beloved again. As Catherine is everything for him, she is the purpose of life. For her single smile, he can do anything. He remains Yesman all the time for her, But at last, he is beaten by his fate, when Catherine passes away. And he is left to loneliness and isolation which pains him psychologically.

Conclusion

In a nutshell. One can say that war and love go to ether in this novel but then love is dominant as compared with war because love appeals to humans emotions while war brings about sufferings so humans are more likely to take interest in love as it happened in the novel but love is a land of spirit which I recognized only when it turns into pain as far as love is not turned into pain is not recognized socially. Obviously, love results in pain either psychological or physical. So in the novel Henry's love when becomes intense spirit for Catherine then at starts teasing him psychologically through his missing and longing feelings. Moreover after the death of Catherine he feels isolated and suffers from the thought of Catherine, which proves that he is in pain which resulted from his love.

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